

interferon regulatory factor 6 (IRF6) : Machine learning discoveries of 2^{nd} order synergy in Meningiomas

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Abstract

Background : IRF6 belongs to interferon regulatory transcription factor (IRF) family that share a highly conserved N-terminal helix-turn-helix DNA-binding domain and a less conserved C-terminal protein-binding domain. It is implicated in Van der Woude syndrome, Popliteal pterygium syndrome, mammary epithelial cells, autophagic-related cancer cell response to tobacco exposure, skin carcinogenesis, muscular differentiation and cytoskeletal formation in the tongue, Hailey-Hailey disease, melanoma, salivary glands, Nasopharyngeal carcinoma, escape of Human papillomavirus type 16, gastric cancer, ankyloblepharon, salivary acinar cells and Sjögren's syndrome, to name a few. However, its role in meningiomas has not yet been determined completely. Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 tumors from all 3 World Health Organization (WHO) grades (I through III) using clinical, gene expression, and sequencing data and using unsupervised clustering analysis identified 3 molecular types (A, B, and C) that reliably predicted recurrence. Further, these groups did not directly correlate with the WHO grading system, which classifies more than half of the tumors in the most aggressive molecular type as benign. **Issue** : Increasing evidence point to the fact that meningioma classification and grading, that is based on histopathology does not always accurately predict tumor aggressiveness and recurrence behaviour and knowledge of the underlying biology of the treatment resistant meningiomas and the impact of genetic alterations in these tumors, is lacking. At the current stage more genomic studies are required to unravel the role of other genes and their interactions with other genetic factors. **Resolution** : In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Adapting this search engine to the Meningioma dataset, i present here 2^{nd} order combinations of IRF6, some of which have been known to exist via wet lab experiments, but many are yet to be tested. The reveals combinations might help oncologists/biologists test possible hypotheses that might be the causing factors in meningioma. Further, in my limited grasp, if proven true, the combinations revealed by the search engine might pave way

*ML dicoveries of IRF6 synergy in Meningiomas

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for development of gene based therapies aimed at resolving pathological issues related to meningiomas.

Keywords: IRF6, Meningioma, Sensitivity analysis, Machine learning.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Meningioma

Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. They arise from the arachnoid cap cells. These arachnoid cap cells are specialized cells that make up the arachnoid mater (one of the three protective membranes covering the brain and spinal cord). The arachnoid mater is one of the three meninges. The other two that constitute the meninges are dura mater and pia mater.

1.1.1. World Health Organization (WHO) classification

The meningiomas are classified into three grades by WHO under the Central Nervous System tumours, namely, Grade I (benign), Grade II (atypical) and Grade III (anaplastic/malignant), based on histopathology or subtype (Louis et al. [3]). As of 2021, there exists 12 histopathological meningioma subtypes according to a mini-review by Torp

et al. [4]. They are meningothelial, fibrous, transitional, psammomatous, angioma-tous, microcystic, secretory, lymphoplasmacyte-rich, atypical, chordoid, clear cell and anaplastic (malignant) meningioma.

1.1.2. Historical perspective

Czarnetzki et al. [5] investigated a skull that was excavated at Steinheim/Murr (Baden-Wurttemberg, Germany) and consisted of a well preserved plagiocephalic cranium, with most of the facial skeleton intact. Their results of stratigraphical dating suggested the fossil specimen of *Homo steinheimensis*, was about 3,65,000 years old. In the fossile, they found that several features of the inner cranial table were consistent with a diagnosis of meningioma.

As documented in Okonkwo and Laws Jr [6], in 1614, Felix Plater, Professor of Medicine, issued a case report from the University of Basel on Caspar Bonecurtius, a noble knight stating -

began to lose his mind gradually over a two year period, to such an extent that finally he was completely stupefied and did nothing rationally. He had no desire for food and ate only when forcibly fed. ... Finally after matters had gone on thus for six months, he died.

Further, the autopsy report of Plater stated the following -

a round fleshy tumor, like an acorn. It was hard and full of holes and was as large as a medium-sized apple. It was covered with its own membrane and was entwined with veins. However, it was free of all connections with the matter of the brain, so much so that when it was removed by hand, it left behind a remarkable cavity.

This was the first case in the history that documented a patient with a lesion that was most compatible with a meningioma.

Next, in a contribution by Italian scientists, Paterniti [7] documents the first contribution of Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri in 1813 in a manuscript *Trattato di Chirurgia Pratica*, which was never published. Its discovery was made accidentally by David Giordano, who referred in detail in an article on surgeon of Pisa in *La chirurgia di Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri*. *Riv Storia Sci MedNat*. 1927: XVIII (3-4): 75-106. The unpublished manuscript of 488 pages describes that Vacca Berlinhieri proposed and performed a most bold radical operation. After a craniectomy with five or six burr holes on the outskirts of the fungus, the tumor was removed together the dura mater from which it originated, tying the cut vessels.

In 1847, Zanobi Pecchioli, Professor of Clinical Surgery and Operative Medicine at Modena and then at Siena University, published an account of surgeries performed during 16 years, from 1832 to 1847 (16 of the 1524 reported operations involved trephining of the skull). In one of these interventions, he carried out on July 29 1835, in Siena, for the resection of a meningioma, a defined fungus of the duramater. The case was not referred in the literature by Pecchioli but was described by in Pecchioli [8]. Finally, Cushing [9] coined the modern term of "meningioma".

Figure 1: A schematic diagram of different pathways in different meningiomas, as provided by Szulzewsky et al. [12] under CC-BY Attribution 4.0 International license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

1.1.3. Pathophysiology

Meningiomas arise from arachnoidal cap cells, most of which are near the vicinity of the venous sinuses, and this is the site of greatest prevalence for meningioma formation. The dural venous sinuses (also called dural/cerebral/cranial sinuses) are venous sinuses (channels) found between the periosteal and meningeal layers of dura mater in the brain. They receive blood from the cerebral veins, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) from the subarachnoid space via arachnoid granulations. They mainly empty into the internal jugular vein. Cranial venous sinuses communicate with veins outside the skull through emissary veins. These communications help to keep the pressure of blood in the sinuses constant. (contributors [10] and Pamir et al. [11]) A schematic diagram for different pathways in different meningiomas has been provided in figure 1.

1.2. interferon regulatory factor 6 (IRF6)

Out of a *Xenopus* neurula cDNA library, Hatada et al. [13] isolated a clone which encoded a 52.4-kDa protein highly similar to the mouse interferon regulatory factor, IRF-6, whose function was unknown. They named this gene xIRF-6, the mRNA of which seemed to be maternally transmitted, but its amount rapidly decreased after the tailbud stage. Whole-mount in situ hybridization showed that xIRF-6 mRNA was expressed in the presumptive somitic mesoderm in the late gastrula, and then confined to a segment of posterior somite during the neurula through the tailbud stage. They hypothesized

that the temporally and spatially limited expression of the xIRF-6 gene product might contribute to the transcriptional regulation of specific genes which are necessary for the development of the posterior somites. Kondo et al. [14] found a nonsense mutation in IRF6 in the affected twin of a pair of monozygotic twins who were discordant for **Van der Woude syndrome** (VWS). Subsequently, they identified mutations in IRF6 in 45 additional unrelated families affected with VWS and distinct mutations in 13 families affected with **Popliteal pterygium syndrome** (PPS). Their expression analyses showed high levels of IRF6 mRNA along the medial edge of the fusing palate, tooth buds, hair follicles, genitalia and skin. Their observations demonstrated that haploinsufficiency of IRF6 disrupted orofacial development and were consistent with dominant-negative mutations disturbing development of the skin and genitalia.

1.3. Roles of IRF6 in different disease

Bailey et al. [15] identified IRF6 as a novel Maspin-interacting protein in **mammary epithelial cells**. Maspin is a tumor suppressor in the breast and has also been implicated in mammary gland morphogenesis. They examined the expression of IRF6 and Maspin during post-utero mammary gland development and their data revealed that the expression of IRF6 and Maspin was temporally and spatially regulated throughout mammary gland development, with maximal expression of both proteins occurring in fully differentiated, lactating lobuloalveolar cells. They further found that IRF6 adopted a luminal localization pattern following complete epithelial cell polarization and present new evidence for the secretion of IRF6 into the milk. Their results supported the hypothesis that IRF6 and Maspin were important for mammary epithelial cell differentiation, and advanced the understanding of the Maspin-IRF6 partnership during normal mammary gland development.

Tobacco-induced oxidative stress leads to chronic inflammation and is implicated in the development of many human epithelial cancers, including head and neck cancer. Ratovitski [16] showed that cigarette smoke exposure induced the expression of the $\Delta Np63\alpha$ and nitric oxide synthase (NOS)-2 in head and neck squamous cell carcinoma cells and immortalized oral keratinocytes. They found that the NOS2 promoter contained various sequences for several transcription factors including IRF-6 and p63, which were shown in vivo binding to the NOS2 promoter in response to smoke exposure. Using small interfering (si)-RNAs against both $\Delta Np63\alpha$ and IRF6, they observed a decrease in the induction of NOS2 promoter-driven reporter luciferase activity and showed inhibition of NOS2 activity. Moreover, they found that both mainstream (MSE) and sidestream (SSE) smoking extracts induced changes in expression of autophagic marker, LC3B, while siRNA against $\Delta Np63\alpha$, IRF6 and NOS2 modulated these autophagic changes. Thus their data supported the notion that $\Delta Np63\alpha$ -IRF6 interplay regulated NOS2 transcription, thereby underlying the **autophagic-related cancer cell response to tobacco exposure**.

Botti et al. [17] hypothesized that IRF6 might be involved in **skin carcinogenesis** and hence, analyzed IRF6 expression in a large series of squamous cell carcinomas (SCCs) and found a strong down-regulation of IRF6 that correlated with tumor invasive and differentiation status. IRF6 down-regulation in SCC cell lines and primary tumors correlates with methylation on a CpG dinucleotide island located in its promoter region.

To identify the molecular mechanisms regulating IRF6 potential tumor suppressive activity, they performed a genome-wide analysis by combining ChIP sequencing for IRF6 binding sites and gene expression profiling in primary human keratinocytes after siRNA-mediated IRF6 depletion, and found that IRF-6 targeted cell cycle-related genes and genes involved in differentiation, cell adhesion, and cell-cell contact. They also found that IRF6 down-regulation promoted invasive behavior and that reintroduction of IRF6 into SCC cells strongly inhibited cell growth. Their results indicated a function for IRF6 in suppression of tumorigenesis in stratified epithelia.

A recent report showed that MCS9.7, an enhancer near IRF-6, was active in the **tongue**, suggesting that IRF-6 might also be expressed in the tongue. Goudy et al. [18] detected IRF-6 staining in the mesoderm-derived muscle during development of the tongue. Dual labeling experiments demonstrated that IRF6 was expressed only in the Myf5+ cell lineage, which originated from the segmental paraxial mesoderm and gives rise to the muscles of the tongue. Fate mapping of the segmental paraxial mesoderm cells revealed a cell-autonomous IRF6 function with reduced and poorly organized Myf5+ cell lineage in the tongue. Their molecular analyses showed that the IRF6^{-/-} embryos had aberrant cytoskeletal formation of the segmental paraxial mesoderm in the tongue. Fate mapping of the cranial neural crest cells revealed non-cell-autonomous IRF-6 function with the loss of the inter-molar eminence. Based on their data, they concluded that IRF-6 played important cell-autonomous and non-cell-autonomous roles in muscular differentiation and cytoskeletal formation in the tongue.

Hailey-Hailey disease (HHD) is caused by heterozygous mutations in the ATP2C1 gene, encoding the secretory pathway Ca²⁺ ATPase1 (SPCA1). SPCA1 and sarco/endoplasmic reticulum Ca²⁺ ATPase2 (SERCA2) encoded by ATP2A2 are two essential calcium pumps needed for Ca²⁺ homeostasis maintenance in keratinocytes. ATP2A2 mutations cause another hereditary skin disorder, Darier's disease (DD). Zhang et al. [19] used the skin biopsy samples from patients with HHD and human primary keratinocytes transfected with ATP2C1 siRNA to search for potential pathogenic mechanisms in HHD. They observed normal SERCA2 levels, but reduced p63, and increased IRF-6 levels in HHD epidermal tissues and SPCA1-deficient keratinocytes. The abnormal expression of p63 and IRF6 appeared to be related to SPCA1 haploinsufficiency, with down-regulation of p63 probably resulting from IRF6 overexpression in HHD. Thus they hypothesized that a novel pathogenic mechanism involving SPCA1, p63, and IRF6 might play a role in the skin lesions occurring in HHD.

Nobeyama and Nakagawa [20] determined the methylation status of the CGI located in the 5' region of IRF-6 (5' IRF-6 CGI) in **melanoma**. They found that the methylation level of the 5' IRF-6 CGI was completely inversely correlated with cell sensitivity to interferon- β in eight examined melanoma cell lines. These methylation levels were high in the melanoma cell lines with suppression of IRF-6 expression and were low in the cell lines with IRF-6 expression. They concluded that IRF6 was aberrantly silenced by DNA methylation of the 5' IRF-6 CGI in melanoma. The methylation status of IRF-6 is potentially associated with the sensitivity of melanoma to interferon.

Around 85% of patients with Van der Woude express pits on the lower lip that continuously or intermittently drain saliva, and patients with the common cleft lip and palate have a higher prevalence of dental caries and gingivitis. Metwalli et al. [21]

aimed to identify the role of IRF6 in development of exocrine glands, specifically the major **salivary glands**. They found high expression of IRF-6 in major and minor salivary glands and ducts. Their immunostaining data also confirmed the endogenous expression of IRF6 in the developing ductal, serous, and mucous acinar cells of salivary glands. Further, they observed that loss of IRF-6 in mice caused an increase in the proliferation level of salivary cells, disorganized branching morphogenesis, and a lack of differentiated mucous acinar cells in submandibular and sublingual glands. In conclusion, their data reported a novel role of IRF-6 in exocrine gland development and supported a rationale for performing exocrine functional tests for patients with IRF-6-damaging mutations.

Nasopharyngeal carcinoma (NPC), which originates from the nasopharynx, is highly prevalent in Southern China and Southeast Asia, and more than 90% of all NPCs are non-keratinizing undifferentiated cells or poorly differentiated squamous cells. Using genomic expression profiling, Xu et al. [22] revealed that IRF-6 was downregulated in highly metastatic NPC cells, cancer stem-like NPC cells and animal models. Their functional assays revealed that elevated IRF-6 expression suppressed cell proliferation, growth, Cancer stem cells (CSCs) properties and enhanced cell chemotherapeutic sensitivity. Further, they determined that as a tumor suppressor gene and transcription factor, IRF6 directly bound the upstream region of the ATP-binding cassette sub-family G member 2 (ABCG2) DNA element and suppressed target ABCG2 expression in NPC cells. Their results, provided the first evidence that IRF-6 directly targeted the ABCG2 gene and selectively kills CSCs in NPC and that IRF6 might be a valuable tool for developing new CSC-targeted treatment strategies for undifferentiated NPC patients.

Human papillomavirus type 16 (HPV16) and other oncoviruses have been shown to block innate immune responses and to persist in the host. However, to avoid viral persistence, the immune response attempts to clear the infection. Ainouze et al. [23] showed that infection of human keratinocytes with HPV16 induced the secretion of IL-1 β . Further, they showed that expression of the viral oncoprotein E6 in human keratinocytes inhibited IRF-6 transcription which they revealed, regulated IL-1 β promoter activity. Via ChIP in tissues from patients with cervical cancer, they showed HPV16 abrogation of p53 binding to the IRF6 promoter. Thus they showed that E6 inhibition of IRF-6 was an escape strategy used by HPV16 to block the production IL-1 β .

Li et al. [24] found that the IRF-6 expression was significantly downregulated in **gastric cancer (GC)**. This downregulation of IRF-6 in GC might be due to the overexpression of ZEB1 and the DNA methylation of IRF6 promoter.

Uddin et al. [25] presented the case of a boy born at 41 weeks' gestational age who was found to have multiple anatomic anomalies, including abnormalities of the oral cavity, eyelids, and digits. He had **ankyloblepharon** that was localized to the lateral portion of the palpebral fissure bilaterally. Their genetic testing confirmed a mutation in the IRF-6. They presented a novel surgical technique for bedside ankyloblepharon repair and described the relevant clinical features of this case.

Pham et al. [26] investigated the mechanism of IRF-6 function in regulating adherens junction proteins and inflammatory cytokines in human **salivary acinar cells** and **Sjögren's syndrome (SS)** biopsies. In IRF6-null mice, they observed myoepithelial cell detachment from acinar cells of major SGs, and the acini were remarkably disorganized compared to wild-type littermates. In human salivary NS-SV-acinar and

adenocarcinoma cells, when they knocked down IRF-6, it resulted in a reduction of β -catenin, RAB11b, and the inflammatory cytokines TGF β 3, IL6, IL17A, and IL22, while IRF-6 overexpression led to an increase in adherens junction proteins and pro-inflammatory cytokines. Consequently, cell-cell contact and junction of acinar cells were disrupted. In SS biopsies, they found that IRF6 level was remarkably elevated in salivary SS affected acini, along with increased levels of E-cadherin and inflammatory cytokines than control biopsies.

Many of the different synergies represented as combinations of genes/proteins have been experimentally tested and published. However, there are combinations that have yet to be explored. I address the problem of identifying these unexplored combinations via use of a machine learning based search engine in the next section.

1.4. Insight behind the work

Across all search engines has the fundamental principle remains the same i.e to capture the pattern available in the data and based on that pattern, rank a list of queries. Different algorithms can be applied, however if the fundamental pattern is captured accurately, then the rankings will remain approximately the same, with slight variations, across the different kinds of search engines used. I use one search engine, however, vary the way the patterns are captured via use of different sensitivity methods. Each sensitivity method uses a different flavour/mathematical formulation to compute the sensitivity indices to estimate the influence of the involved factors. These involved factors are genes that play a role in cell biology, in the above research. The insight is that all methods will capture the sensitivity of the involved factors based on their recorded regulations and the search engine will rank the combination of factors based on these sensitivity indices. Since the role of involved factors are captured properly, the search engine will give appropriate rankings to the combinations, thus capturing which gene combinations might be playing significantly in a biological phenomena. The above work shows rankings for experimentally confirmed combinations as well as unexplored/untested combinations. These rankings are not just numbers. They point to the existence of biological synergy in the form of gene combinations, whether tested in wet lab or unexplored till now. Finally, the findings suggest that the rankings are conserved across the different sensitivity methods used.

1.5. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [27] in https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2nd order gene combinations. The sensitivity package by Pujol et al. [28] was used to develop the search engine pipeline. The current research uses the Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion (HSIC) and SOBOL method, implemented in the sensitivity package mentioned above. I use three different kernels under the HSIC method namely, • laplace, • linear and • rbf. For SOBOL method, I use • sobol-2002, and • sobol-jansen. Each of these variants or kernels have been implemented in the sensitivity package and option

has been provided in the search engine code to generate the rankings for a particular gene, using a choice of a kernel/variant at a time. Technical details about the variants and kernels can be found in references cited in Pujol et al. [28].

2. Methods

2.1. Static data from Patel et al. [1]

Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 meningioma samples from 140 patients, and according to the WHO histopathological classification system for meningioma, they found 121 tumors were of grade I (benign), 32 were of grade II (atypical), and 7 were of grade III (malignant). To determine whether meningiomas could be differentiated based on gene expression profiles, they used principal component analysis (PCA) on a discovery set of 97 tumors (i.e 77 WHO grade I and 20 WHO grade II). Next, they employed nonnegative matrix factorization (NMF) clustering (a unsupervised machine-learning approach) for $k = 2$ to $k = 7$ using the 1,500 genes that varied most among the tumor samples. They report that after 1,000 iterations, 3 clusters ($k = 3$) emerged as providing the best fit as determined by the consensus membership, cophenetic, and silhouette scores. They evaluated the cluster significance of the 3 subtypes using SigClust (Huang et al. [29]) and observed statistical significance between cluster boundaries, which exhibited significant differences in WHO grade representation.

2.2. Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]

The procedure begins with the listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes. Here n can be the choice of the biologist. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represent a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. Since the sensitivity analysis methods require a sample for a particular observation, a steep gaussian distribution was generated with a jitter (noise) added to the deviation from the reported point measurement of 0.005. In this experiment, the distribution contained 10 measurements (including the point of measurement under consideration). This is repeated for each point of measurement.

To have an averaged ranking, the experiment was designed to run for 25 iterations. In each iteration, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in a required format. Details of formatting the data have not been presented in the article to maintain the fluidity and brevity. Interested readers can find examples of formatting the data in the sensitivity analysis package in R. Sensitivity analysis and its relevance in systems biology have been covered in a recently published article by Sinha [30], which forms the foundation for this work. After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, for a chosen sensitivity analysis method, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Here, the indices are averaged per combination to have a mean index value. These index values form the discriminative features for a particular combination. For a k^{th} order combination, a vector of k elements or indices forms a feature vector. Thus for C_k^n combinations there will be C_k^n vectors, each containing k elements. Next, SVM_{learn}^{Rank} Joachims [27] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [27]. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R Team [31], in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use source("extractMeningiomadata.R") • use source("manuscript-2-2.R") • use source("SVMRank-Results-S-mean.R").

2.3. Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R

The execution begins by some preprocessing of the file containing the information regarding the down regulated genes via `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")`. The library containing the sensitivity analysis methods is then loaded in the interface using the command `library(sensitivity)` (Note - this package can be downloaded for free from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sensitivity/index.html>). Next a gaussian distribution for a particular transcript level for a gene is generated to have a sample. This is needed in the computation of sensitivity index for that particular gene. A gene of particular choice is selected (in blue) and the choice of the combination is made (here $k = 2$). Later a kernel is used (here rbf for HSIC method). 25 different indices are generated which help in generating aggregate rank using these 25 indices. The Support vector ranking algorithm is employed to generate the scores for different combinations and these scores are then sorted out. This is done using the command `source("SVMRank - Results - S - mean.R")`. A file is generated that contains the combinations in increasing order of influence. Note that 1 means lowest rank and vice versa, for 2^{nd} order combinations for any gene using a particular density based sensitivity index.

2.4. Regarding biological insight

For the recorded gene expression values, the sensitivity indices are computed. The search engine uses the kernel based density method. The kernel method takes the data, that is in a lower dimensional plane and projects it to a higher dimensional plane, with an idea that in a higher dimensional place, there exists a dot product between the projected data. To simply state, the idea is that in a higher dimensional plane the non-linearities between the data (in lower dimensional plane) will be captured and the data

may be segregated from each other via a hyperplane. So, irrespective of the method used to measure the gene expression values, if the measurements capture biological information (to whatever extent they can), then the kernel method will be able to capture the nonlinearities/synergies, if existing and allow the sensitivity analysis method (here density based method) to estimate the strength of influence of each of the factors. Based on the sensitivity indices of combinations of a particular order, the search engine ranks the combinations. Details of search engine are provided in the published work in Sinha [2].

It is important to note that the search engine will not give insight about the mechanism of synergy between the components of a combination. However, if the synergy exists between components of an unexplored/untested combination, then the sensitivity indices will capture the influence of these components taken together (which form a combination of interest) and will rank the combination appropriately. These rankings provide insight about which combination a biologist/oncologist might want to test in a forest of combinations for a given scenario in a cell (whether normal or pathological).

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. IRF6 related synergies

Note - IRF6 was found to be upregulated in Type A. Upregulation was defined as Type logFC to be > 1 and $FDR \leq 0.001$, in Patel et al. [1]. Also, sorting of scores by the machine learning algorithm were done in ascending order, i.e - top is lowest in ranking. A total of 307 2^{nd} order combinations of IRF6 were recorded.

3.1.1. IRF6 - individual genes

The following genes in combination with IRF6 showed high rankings - USH1 protein network component harmonin (USH1C), G protein-coupled receptor class C group 5 member A (GPRC5A), tollid like 1 (TLL1), mucolipin TRP cation channel 3 (MCOLN3), erb-b2 receptor tyrosine kinase 3 (ERBB3), ribosomal protein S6 kinase A2 (RPS6KA2), RAP1 GTPase activating protein (RAP1GAP), secretagogen, EF-hand calcium binding protein (SCGN), ATP binding cassette subfamily B member 1 (ABCB1), parathyroid hormone like hormone (PTH1H), neurotensin receptor 1 (NTSR1), mesothelin (MSLN), cordon-bleu WH2 repeat protein (COBL), protein arginine methyltransferase 8 (PRMT8), leucine rich repeat containing 31 (LRRC31), peroxisomal biogenesis factor 5 like (PEX5L), interleukin 1 receptor like 1 (IL1RL1), melanophilin (MLPH), 24-dehydrocholesterol reductase (DHCR24), tetraspanin 1 (TSPAN1), polypeptide N-acetylgalactosaminyltransferase 12 (GALNT12), transmembrane protein 54 (TMEM54), G protein signaling modulator 2 (GSPM2), tubulin alpha 4a (TUBA4A), beta-1,4-mannosyl-glycoprotein 4-beta-N-acetylglucosaminyltransferase (MGAT3), LIF interleukin 6 family cytokine (LIF), filamin C (FLNC), leucine rich repeat containing 4 (LRRC4), coiled-coil domain containing 136 (CCDC136), myosin VC (MYO5C), low density lipoprotein receptor (LDLR), afadin, adherens junction formation factor (AFDN), argininosuccinate synthase 1 (ASS1), castor zinc finger 1 (CASZ1), tetratricopeptide

repeat domain 9 (TTC9), RAB33A, member RAS oncogene family (RAB33A), ETS homologous factor (EHF), proline rich and Gla domain 4 (PRRG4), protein phosphatase 1 regulatory inhibitor subunit 1A (PPP1R1A), KLF transcription factor 4 (KLF4), KIAA0319 (KIAA0319), FXFD domain containing ion transport regulator 6 (FXFD6), p21 (RAC1) activated kinase 6 (PAK6), GIPC PDZ domain containing family member 2 (GIPC2), HECT, C2 and WW domain containing E3 ubiquitin protein ligase 2 (HECW2), HECT and RLD domain containing E3 ubiquitin protein ligase 5 (HERC5), RasGEF domain family member 1B (RASGEF1B), shisa like 1 (KIAA1644 / SHISAL1), ring finger protein 157 (RNF157), solute carrier family 47 member 1 (SLC47A1), PR/SET domain 16 (PRDM16), solute carrier family 44 member 3 (SLC44A3), polypeptide N-acetylgalactosaminyltransferase 13 (GALNT13), atypical chemokine receptor 3 (ACKR3), coiled-coil domain 39 molecular ruler complex subunit (CCDC39), serine protease 35 (PRSS35), calcium voltage-gated channel auxiliary subunit alpha2delta 1 (CACNA2D1), neural cell adhesion molecule 2 (NCAM2), solute carrier family 26 member 2 (SLC26A2), chloride intracellular channel 2 (CLIC2), SH3 domain containing ring finger 2 (SH3RF2), STEAP2 metalloredoxase (STEAP2), nucleophosmin/nucleoplasmin 2 (NPM2), angiotensin I converting enzyme (ACE), spondin 2 (SPON2), cytochrome P450 family 3 subfamily A member 4 (CYP3A4), NHS like 3 (KIAA1522 / NHSL3), Rho guanine nucleotide exchange factor 3 (ARHGEF3), sphingomyelin synthase 2 (SGMS2), solute carrier family 9 member B2 (SLC9B2), FHF complex subunit HOOK interacting protein 1A (FAM160A1 / FHIP1A), ankyrin repeat domain 33B (ANKRD33B), adenylate cyclase 1 (ADCY1), lysine demethylase 1B (KDM1B), protein phosphatase 1 regulatory subunit 36 (PPP1R36), calcium voltage-gated channel auxiliary subunit beta 2 (CACNB2), serine peptidase inhibitor, Kunitz type 1 (SPINT1), sodium voltage-gated channel beta subunit 3 (SCN3B), serpin family B member 8 (SERPINB8), pleckstrin homology domain containing A7 (PLEKHA7), alanyl aminopeptidase, membrane (ANPEP), small G protein signaling modulator 1 (SGSM1), OTU deubiquitinase 7A (OTUD7A), potassium two pore domain channel subfamily K member 3 (KCNK3), cilia and flagella associated protein 46 (CFAP46), interferon stimulated exonuclease gene 20 (ISG20), serine palmitoyltransferase long chain base subunit 3 (SPTLC3), bisphosphoglycerate mutase (BPGM), regulator of calcineurin 2 (RCAN2), carboxylesterase 4A (CES4A), primary cilia formation / ciliary microtubule associated protein 3 (PIFO / CIMAP3), solute carrier organic anion transporter family member 2A1 (SLCO2A1), solute carrier family 35 member G1 (SLC35G1), family with sequence similarity 91 member A1 (FAM91A1), LRRN4 C-terminal like (LRRN4CL), G protein-coupled receptor 4 (GPR4), endoplasmic reticulum to nucleus signaling 1 (ERN1), WSC domain containing 1 (WSCD1), synemin (SYNM), calpain 12 (CAPN12), MAF bZIP transcription factor F (MAFF), transcobalamin 2 (TCN2), insulin induced gene 1 (INSIG1), BCR activator of RhoGEF and GTPase (BCR), natural killer cell cytotoxicity receptor 3 ligand 1 (NCR3LG1), family with sequence similarity 78 member B (FAM78B), solute carrier family 6 member 9 (SLC6A9), laminin subunit beta 3 (LAMB3), ectonucleotide pyrophosphatase/phosphodiesterase 1 (ENPP1), AFDN divergent transcript (AFDN-DT), SH3 domain binding glutamate rich protein like 2 (SH3BGRL2), sterol regulatory element binding transcription factor 2 (SREBF2) and collagen type XV alpha 1 chain (COL15A1).

Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I tabulate the rankings

of 2nd order combination of IRF6 with the above list, that were reported to be upregulated in Patel et al. [1]. Table 1 and 2 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 3 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1 and 2.

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS IRF6									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T IRF6									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
USH1C - IRF6	213	265	242	235	GPRC5A - IRF6	292	220	152	306
TLL1 - IRF6	274	136	167	236	MCOLN3 - IRF6	286	168	192	271
ERBB3 - IRF6	254	242	158	113	RPS6KA2 - IRF6	189	156	23	225
RAP1GAP - IRF6	223	247	216	301	SCGN - IRF6	36	190	219	307
ABCB1 - IRF6	290	230	199	276	PTHLH - IRF6	207	252	169	265
NTSR1 - IRF6	253	157	130	266	MSLN - IRF6	157	233	218	188
COBL - IRF6	111	240	191	191	PRMT8 - IRF6	279	155	217	297
LRR31 - IRF6	204	202	176	58	PEX5L - IRF6	216	150	263	249
IL1RL1 - IRF6	269	297	306	256	MLPH - IRF6	295	215	84	215
DHCR24 - IRF6	176	238	233	10	TSPAN1 - IRF6	250	239	97	262
GALNT12 - IRF6	190	292	290	197	TMEM54 - IRF6	244	176	254	204
GPSM2 - IRF6	270	140	175	229	TUBA4A - IRF6	174	251	186	98
MGAT3 - IRF6	219	278	150	132	LIF - IRF6	159	293	213	208
FLNC - IRF6	220	228	293	97	LRR4 - IRF6	181	164	240	220
CCDC136 - IRF6	243	225	209	140	MYO5C - IRF6	293	291	284	209
LDLR - IRF6	300	208	251	90	AFDN - IRF6	53	257	303	255
ASS1 - IRF6	258	270	294	201	CASZ1 - IRF6	222	196	179	122
TTC9 - IRF6	302	243	145	174	RAB33A - IRF6	282	232	229	202
EHF - IRF6	170	221	212	23	PRRG4 - IRF6	276	192	208	218
PPP1R1A - IRF6	305	273	63	244	KLF4 - IRF6	144	299	153	195
KIAA0319 - IRF6	283	170	256	175	FXD6 - IRF6	24	165	244	221
PAK6 - IRF6	264	269	307	193	GIPC2 - IRF6	251	245	178	264
HECW2 - IRF6	188	199	246	92	HERC5 - IRF6	193	250	262	226
RASGEF1B - IRF6	236	177	291	186	KIAA1644 - IRF6	241	235	125	303
RNF157 - IRF6	256	77	273	258	SLC47A1 - IRF6	291	258	249	238
PRDM16 - IRF6	164	284	257	139	SLC44A3 - IRF6	200	261	305	121
GALNT13 - IRF6	155	162	65	272	ACKR3 - IRF6	299	272	174	15
CCDC39 - IRF6	245	259	298	162	PRSS35 - IRF6	263	262	194	172

Table 1: 2nd order interaction ranking between IRF6 VS Individual members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 and 2 graphically, with the following influences - • Individual members w.r.t IRF6 with IRF6 – > USH1C / GPRC5A / TLL1 / MCOLN3 / ERBB3 / RPS6KA2 / RAP1GAP / SCGN / ABCB1 / PTHLH / NTSR1 / MSLN / COBL / PRMT8 / LRR31 / PEX5L / IL1RL1 / MLPH / DHCR24 / TSPAN1 / GALNT12 / TMEM54 / GPSM2 / TUBA4A / MGAT3 / LIF / FLNC / LRR4 / CCDC136 / MYO5C / LDLR / AFDN / ASS1 / CASZ1 / TTC9 / RAB33A / EHF / PRRG4 / PPP1R1A / KLF4 / KIAA0319 / FXD6 / PAK6 / GIPC2 / HECW2 / HERC5 / RASGEF1B / KIAA1644 / RNF157 / SLC47A1 / PRDM16 / SLC44A3 / GALNT13 / ACKR3 / CCDC39 / PRSS35 / CACNA2D1 / NCAM2 / SLC26A2 / CLIC2 / SH3RF2 / STEAP2 / NPM2 / ACE / SPON2 / CYP3A4 / KIAA1522 / ARHGEF3 / SGMS2 / SLC9B2 / FAM160A1 / ANKRD33B / ADCY1 / KDM1B / PPP1R36 / CACNB2 / SPINT1 / SCN3B / SERPINB8 / PLEKHA7 / ANPEP / SGSM1 / OTUD7A / KCNK3 / CFAP46 / ISG20 / SPTLC3 / BPGM / RCAN2 / CES4A / PIFO

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS IRF6									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T IRF6									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
CACNA2D1 - IRF6	294	271	253	207	NCAM2 - IRF6	235	188	285	151
SLC26A2 - IRF6	146	205	177	210	CLIC2 - IRF6	224	267	225	182
SH3RF2 - IRF6	262	41	187	206	STEAP2 - IRF6	201	167	235	102
NPM2 - IRF6	284	216	283	157	ACE - IRF6	208	288	198	200
SPON2 - IRF6	217	86	259	296	CYP3A4 - IRF6	229	234	171	142
KIAA1522 - IRF6	203	298	282	217	ARHGEF3 - IRF6	273	289	299	168
SGMS2 - IRF6	221	163	274	149	SLC9B2 - IRF6	296	255	297	189
FAM160A1 - IRF6	187	206	173	40	ANKRD33B - IRF6	125	279	275	211
ADCY1 - IRF6	205	263	281	164	KDM1B - IRF6	177	179	271	150
PPP1R36 - IRF6	271	304	108	288	CACNB2 - IRF6	281	119	248	183
SPINT1 - IRF6	297	285	228	234	SCN3B - IRF6	252	183	289	72
SERPINB8 - IRF6	121	231	162	232	PLEKHA7 - IRF6	175	301	300	173
ANPEP - IRF6	232	276	161	190	SGSM1 - IRF6	218	295	106	212
OTUD7A - IRF6	209	213	279	187	KCNK3 - IRF6	191	158	56	205
CFAP46 - IRF6	280	281	223	167	ISG20 - IRF6	198	275	181	247
SPTLC3 - IRF6	306	219	222	152	BPGM - IRF6	152	266	236	237
RCAN2 - IRF6	307	184	144	228	CES4A - IRF6	158	303	183	120
PIFO - IRF6	285	296	260	194	SLCO2A1 - IRF6	154	212	154	42
SLC35G1 - IRF6	272	254	302	292	FAM91A1 - IRF6	288	135	258	179
LRRN4CL - IRF6	210	253	255	134	GPR4 - IRF6	182	171	202	178
ERN1 - IRF6	298	224	286	251	WSCD1 - IRF6	260	217	214	108
SYNM - IRF6	172	193	239	261	CAPN12 - IRF6	184	151	280	230
MAFF - IRF6	266	195	172	88	TCN2 - IRF6	259	287	304	127
INSIG1 - IRF6	278	248	231	154	BCR - IRF6	153	175	210	160
NCR3LG1 - IRF6	35	241	296	231	FAM78B - IRF6	183	154	149	291
SLC6A9 - IRF6	186	203	211	144	LAMB3 - IRF6	178	197	203	170
ENPP1 - IRF6	265	264	190	85	AFDN-DT - IRF6	180	307	247	99
SH3BGRL2 - IRF6	301	191	261	119	SREBF2 - IRF6	240	182	292	203
COL15A1 - IRF6	173	112	267	165					

Table 2: 2nd order interaction ranking between IRF6 VS Individual members.

/ SLCO2A1 / SLC35G1 / FAM91A1 / LRRN4CL / GPR4 / ERN1 / WSCD1 / SYNM / CAPN12 / MAFF / TCN2 / INSIG1 / BCR / NCR3LG1 / FAM78B / SLC6A9 / LAMB3 / ENPP1 / AFDN-DT / SH3BGRL2 / SREBF2 / COL15A1

Table 3: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between IRF6 and Individual members.

4. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic IRF6 2nd order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the ranking methods it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations of IRF6-X that might be prevalent in meningioma.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

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Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Patel et al. [1]. Permission to use, granted by PNAS.

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